

ORGANIC WASTE

Organic residues, amendments and waste applied on agricultural fields need to be analysed to maintain a high environmental quality standard.

WHAT IS IN IT?

The absence of potentially polluting substances and hazardous elements is mandatory!

IT'S ALL ABOUT THE MONEY...

How to avoid expensive, time-consuming laboratory analysis? DIY with this device!

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IS THERE A SIMPLE WAY TO ANALYSE ORGANIC WASTE?

A portable X-ray device is the answer!

This device enables precise testing in the field within minutes at low cost for a large range of elements.

The tool allows on-site decision making and is also compatible with other fast spectroscopic techniques.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply.

<https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT PROBEFIELD

ProbeField aims to develop a novel protocol for robust in field monitoring of carbon stocks and soil fertility based on proximal sensors and existing soil spectral libraries.

PROJECT COORDINATOR:

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Understanding how soil-carbon sequestration can contribute to climate change mitigation at the regional level and accounting for carbon

SOIL MISSION: conserve soil organic carbon stocks, reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL funded project:
ProbeField

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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